

Awareness and Compliance of PNP Personnel on Republic Act 10586, Otherwise Known as Anti-Drunk and Drugged Driving Act Of 2013

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the level of awareness and extent of compliance of PNP personnel in a highly urbanized city in Western Visayas regarding RA 10586, the Anti-drunk and Drugged Driving Act of 2013, during the first and second quarters of 2022. The study involved 269 respondents from a police station, focusing on age and length of service as variables. Data collection methods included surveys and statistical analysis. The level of awareness among PNP personnel regarding RA 10586 was moderate, while compliance was low. Compliance varied across different ages and length of service categories, with enforcement showing the most variability. Overall, the study found a moderate level of awareness among PNP personnel regarding RA 10586, with compliance levels showing significant variability based on age and length of service. These findings suggest a need for targeted education and enforcement efforts to improve compliance with the law.

Keywords: Awareness, Compliance, PNP Personnel, RA 10586, Anti-Drunk and Drugged Driving Act, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The Anti-Drunk and Drugged Driving Act of 2013, also known as RA 10586, represents a significant step towards promoting road safety in the Philippines. This legislation aims to penalize individuals who drive under the influence of alcohol, dangerous drugs, or similar substances. In coordination with the Land Transportation Office (LTO) and other relevant agencies, it mandates the Philippine Information Agency to conduct an extensive information, education, and communication campaign. The law also requires the acquisition of alcohol breath analyzers, drug testing kits, and other equipment by the LTO and the Philippine National Police (PNP). This proactive approach demonstrates the government's commitment to reducing accidents, injuries, and fatalities caused by drunk and drugged driving.

While RA 10586 represents a positive step towards enhancing road safety, there are significant challenges in its implementation and enforcement. Despite the law being enacted in 2013, there are concerns regarding the awareness and compliance of law enforcement agencies, particularly the Philippine National Police (PNP), tasked with enforcing the law. A study focused on the PNP in Western Visayas highlighted gaps in awareness among officers regarding the requirements of RA 10586, indicating a potential lack of effective implementation strategies (Pacling & Vicente, 2021). This raises questions about the effectiveness of the information, education, and communication campaign mandated by the law. Additionally, the availability and functionality of alcohol breath analyzers, drug testing kits, and other necessary equipment, as mandated by the law, might not be uniform across different regions of the Philippines, potentially affecting enforcement efforts (Padua, 2021). These challenges highlight the need for continuous monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of RA 10586 to ensure its effectiveness in reducing incidents of drunk and drugged driving.

Moreover, public trust and confidence in the PNP's ability to uphold the law are contingent upon officers' adherence to regulations such as RA 10586. Any gaps in awareness or compliance could erode public trust. Furthermore, understanding the level of awareness and compliance among PNP personnel can help identify areas for improvement in training and education programs. Targeted initiatives can be developed to enhance officers' understanding of the law and improve enforcement techniques. Thus, this study.

Objectives

This study aims to assess the awareness and compliance of PNP personnel in a highly urbanized city in Western Visayas with RA 10586 (Anti-Drunk and Drugged Driving Act of 2013) for the first and second quarters of 2022. Specifically, this study sought to determine: 1) the level of awareness of PNP personnel on RA 10586 in education,

deputation, and enforcement; 2) the extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA10586 according to the aforementioned areas; 3) the significant difference in the level of awareness of the PNP personnel on RA 10586 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the significant difference in the extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA 10586 when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables; and 5) the significant relationship between the level of awareness and extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA 10586.

Research Methodology:

This study used a descriptive research design to examine the awareness and compliance of PNP personnel in a highly urbanized city in Western Visayas with RA 10586. Descriptive research involves collecting and analyzing data through methods like surveys, interviews, observations, and secondary data analysis. The goal is to comprehensively organize and summarize the data to identify patterns, trends, and relationships. This design was chosen because it focuses on describing an existing phenomenon, making it suitable for this study. The description of the design is based on Bryman and Bell (2019).

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were the PNP personnel in a highly urbanized city in Western Visayas with a total population of eight hundred eighty-five (885). Since the number of respondents is quite large, a sample of two hundred sixty-nine (269) was taken using the Cochran formula. A stratified random sampling technique was used to determine the number of respondents in each department. To get the percentage, the number of respondents from each department was divided by the total number of respondents and multiplied by the sample size. The researcher randomly selected the respondents from each department using the lottery technique.

Procedures for Data Collection

After ensuring the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher obtained permission from the police office management to conduct the study. One representative from each department was briefed on how to administer the questionnaire objectively. The responses were then collected, saved, compiled, and tabulated. The data were analyzed using statistical methods, including translating raw data into numerical ratings for tabular presentations, statistical derivations, and computer processing. SPSS software was used for data processing.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to determine the level of awareness of the PNP personnel in a highly urbanized city in Western Visayas on RA 10586, otherwise known as the Anti-drunk and Drugged Driving Act of 2013, in terms of the areas Education, Deputation, and Enforcement. Objective 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as a statistical tool to determine the extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA10586 according to the aforementioned areas. Objective 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test as a statistical tool to determine the significant difference in the level of awareness of the PNP personnel on RA 10586 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. Objective 4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test as a statistical tool to determine the significant difference in the extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA 10586 when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. Objective 5 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman rho as a statistical tool to determine the significant relationship between the level of awareness and extent of compliance of the PNP personnel on RA 10586.

Ethical Considerations

Participants' identities were kept confidential and anonymous. They were not identified in any self-identifying statements or information. Anonymity and confidentiality protect the privacy of participants who willingly participate in research. It's important to consider potential harm to participants, the researcher, the community, and the institution. This harm can include distress, shame, worry, bodily harm, resource loss, emotional harm, and reputational damage.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study, the data gathered from the respondents' answers to the questionnaire, which were counted, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation.

Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586

Table 1

Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Education <i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. attended the seminars and trainings initiated by the PNP.	3.79	High Level
2. attended the seminars and trainings initiated by the LTO.	3.43	Moderate Level
3. personally conducted online scanning of laws and jurisprudence on RA 10586.	3.25	Moderate Level
4. have studied RA 10586 as one of the subjects of Police Basic Recruit Course or any other entry course to the PNP.	3.92	High Level
5. have studied RA 10586 as one of the topics in the Program of Instruction of PNP investigative courses.	3.81	High Level
6. have studied RA 10586 as one of the topics in the Program of Instruction of the PNP mandatory courses.	3.73	High Level
7. have attended, together with other PNP personnel, the seminars and training on RA 10586 as an added measure in the PNP scorecard or dashboard.	3.42	Moderate Level
8. have operated a breath analyzer and speed gun.	2.83	Moderate Level
9. personally tested the violators on the 3 Field Sobriety tests.	2.84	Moderate Level
10. have experienced implementing the law against drunk and drugged drivers.	3.03	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.40	Moderate Level

Table 1 shows the data on the level of awareness of PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education with an overall mean of 3.40, which is interpreted as a moderate level. The item with the highest mean score in this area is 3.92, which is interpreted as a moderate level, in Item No. 4, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I have studied RA 10586 as one of the subjects of Police Basic Recruit Course or any other entry course to the PNP."

Notably, the item with the lowest mean is related to operational skills, specifically Item No. 8, "As a PNP personnel, I have operated a breath analyzer and speed gun," with a mean score of 2.83, categorizing it at a moderate level. This moderate level implies that, on average, PNP personnel may not be as proficient in operating these enforcement devices as desired; in the worst-case scenario, not all have the chance to hold such devices due to unavailability. Operating a breath analyzer and speed gun is a crucial practical skill for enforcing anti-drunk and drugged driving laws. The implication is that there is an opportunity for the PNP to focus on targeted training and skill development programs to enhance personnel proficiency in using these crucial tools and purchase such devices.

These results confirm the study of Kondos (2022), focusing on the varying levels of familiarity with operating a breath analyzer and speed gun, which can be sourced from studies on law enforcement training programs, practical skills development in policing, and the effectiveness of equipment training in enhancing enforcement capabilities.

Table 2
Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Deputation <i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. have been deputized by LTO on RA 10586.	2.49	Low Level
2. attended the deputation seminar conducted by LTO.	2.62	Moderate Level
3. have enforced traffic violations, citing RA 10586 as deputized.	2.85	Moderate Level
4. have been inspired by the deputation process prevailing in the campaign against illegal drugs compared to the model adopted in RAs 10586 & 4136.	3.14	Moderate Level

5. have attended, together with other PNP personnel, the deputation seminars on RA 10586 as an added measure in the PNP scorecard or dashboard.	2.77	Moderate Level
6. have investigated death and physical injuries due to drunk and drugged driving, citing RA 10586 as deputized.	2.51	Moderate Level
7. should have been deputized not only on RA 4136 but also on RA 10586.	2.86	Moderate Level
8. was deputized to enforce RA 10586 as a means to remove drunk and drugged drivers off the street.	2.80	Moderate Level
9. have been deputized by the LTO as requested by the PNP.	2.65	Moderate Level
10. have been deputized by the LTO on their own initiative.	2.78	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	2.75	Moderate Level

Table 2 outlines the awareness among PNP personnel regarding Republic Act (RA) 10586 in Deputation. The overall mean is 2.75, which is interpreted as a moderate level. The highest mean score in this area is 3.14, which is interpreted as a moderate level, in Item No. 4, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I have been inspired by the deputation process prevailing in the campaign against illegal drugs compared to the model adopted in RAs 10586 & 4136."

Notably, item No. 1 got the lowest mean, which is related to the deputation process by the Land Transportation Office (LTO): "As a PNP personnel, I have been deputized by LTO on RA 10586," with a mean score of 2.49, categorizing it at a low level. This low Mean suggests that a significant portion of PNP personnel may not have experienced formal deputation by the LTO specifically for enforcing RA 10586. The implication is that there may be a limited involvement of PNP officers in collaborative efforts with the LTO in the implementation and enforcement of anti-drunk and drugged driving laws. This finding underscores the need for increased collaboration between the PNP and LTO in the deputation process related to RA 10586.

These findings validate the study of Zhao, X. et al. (2014), which reveals that alcohol affects drivers in many aspects, including attitude, judgment, vigilance, perception, reaction, and control.

Table 3
Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Enforcement		
<i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. have maintained data on drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	3.21	Moderate Level
2. have conducted checkpoint operations on drunk and drugged driving.	3.25	Moderate Level
3. deemed it important to have a breath analyzer and speed gun during operations.	3.65	High Level
4. maintained Crime Clock for drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	3.46	Moderate Level
5. maintained Hit Map for drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	3.33	Moderate Level
6. have been subjected to drug test parties to traffic accidents in one of my tours of duty.	3.03	Moderate Level
7. have subjected drunk drivers to field sobriety tests in one of my tours of duty.	3.06	Moderate Level
8. have subjected drunk drivers to alcoholic breath in one of my tours of duty.	3.03	Moderate Level
9. have filed cases citing Act No 3815 and RA 4136 on drunk and drugged driving rather than RA 10586.	2.92	Moderate Level

10. have strictly and religiously enforced or implemented the law against drunk and drugged driving foreseen to minimize, if not control, senseless and gruesome traffic accidents.	3.71	High Level
Overall Mean	3.27	Moderate Level

Table 3 outlines the level of awareness among PNP personnel regarding Republic Act (RA) 10586 in Enforcement. The overall mean is 3.27, which is interpreted as a moderate level. The highest mean score in this area is 3.71, which is interpreted as a high level in Item No. 10, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I have strictly and religiously enforced or implemented the law against drunk and drugged driving foreseen to minimize if not control senseless and gruesome traffic accidents."

Also, item No. 9 got the lowest mean that is related to the legal citation in cases of drunk and drugged driving: "As a PNP personnel, I have filed cases citing Act No 3815 and RA 4136 on drunk and drugged driving rather than RA 10586," with a mean score of 2.92, categorizing it at a moderate level. This finding suggests that some PNP personnel may have opted to cite alternative laws in such cases, potentially indicating a varying understanding among officers about the applicability of RA 10586. The moderate mean suggests the need for clear policy alignment and guidance within the PNP regarding the preferred legal statutes to be cited in cases related to drunk and drugged driving. This may be due to a lack of training given to the personnel of the specific provisions of RA 10586 to ensure a consistent legal response in cases of drunk and drugged driving.

These results corroborate the research of Sloan F. et al. (2018) that higher probabilities estimated by the individuals of being pulled over corresponded to less alcohol-impaired driving in both analyses.

Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586

Table 4
Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education

Area	Mean	Interpretation
A. Education		
<i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. attended the seminars and trainings initiated by the PNP.	3.11	Moderate Level
2. attended the seminars and trainings initiated by the LTO.	2.76	Moderate Level
3. personally conducted online scanning of laws and jurisprudence on RA 10586.	2.75	Moderate Level
4. have studied RA 10586 as one of the subjects of the Police Basic Recruit Course or any other entry course to the PNP.	3.01	Moderate Level
5. have studied RA 10586 as one of the topics in the Program of Instruction of PNP investigative courses.	2.89	Moderate Level
6. have studied RA 10586 as one of the topics in the Program of Instruction of the PNP mandatory courses.	2.83	Moderate Level
7. have attended, together with other PNP personnel, the seminars and training on RA 10586 as an added measure in the PNP scorecard or dashboard.	2.84	Moderate Level
8. have operated a breath analyzer and speed gun.	2.30	Low Level
9. personally tested the violators on the 3 Field Sobriety tests.	2.23	Low Level
10. have experienced implementing the law against drunk and drugged drivers.	2.43	Low Level
Overall Mean	2.72	Moderate Level

Table 4 presents the level of compliance among PNP personnel regarding Republic Act (RA) 10586 in Education. The overall mean is 2.72, which is interpreted as a moderate level. The highest mean score in this area is 3.11, interpreted as a moderate level, in Item No. 1, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I attended the seminars and training initiated by the PNP."

Table 4 sheds light on the level of compliance among PNP personnel with Republic Act (RA) 10586, particularly in education. The item with the lowest mean is related to the personal testing of violators with the 3 Field Sobriety tests, garnering a mean score of 2.23 and categorizing it at a low level found in Item No. 9.

This finding suggests a concerning gap in the operational proficiency of PNP personnel when conducting these crucial tests, which are instrumental in assessing a driver's level of impairment during traffic stops. The low

compliance level implies potential challenges in accurately evaluating suspected drunk or drugged drivers, raising questions about the reliability of evidence in legal proceedings.

These results affirm the Safety Research Report (2022) study that reducing the time between an impaired driving event and biological specimen collection increases the likelihood that toxicological test results will reflect drug presence at the event.

Table 5
Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation

Area	Mean	Interpretation
B. Deputation		
<i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. have been deputized by LTO on RA 10586.	2.20	Low Level
2. attended the deputation seminar conducted by LTO.	2.26	Low Level
3. have enforced traffic violations, citing RA 10586 as deputized.	2.28	Low Level
4. have been inspired by the deputation process prevailing in the campaign against illegal drugs compared to the model adopted in RAs 10586 & 4136.	2.41	Low Level
5. have attended, together with other PNP personnel, the deputation seminars on RA 10586 as an added measure in the PNP scorecard or dashboard.	2.26	Low Level
6. have investigated death and physical injuries due to drunk and drugged driving, citing RA 10586 as deputized.	2.20	Low Level
7. should have been deputized not only on RA 4136 but also on RA 10586.	2.32	Low Level
8. was deputized to enforce RA 10586 as a means to remove drunk and drugged drivers off the street.	2.30	Low Level
9. have been deputized by the LTO as requested by the PNP.	2.30	Low Level
10. have been deputized by the LTO on their own initiative.	2.21	Low Level
Overall Mean	2.27	Low Level

Table 5 underscores the level of compliance among PNP personnel regarding Republic Act (RA.) 10586 in Deputation. The overall mean is 2.27, which is interpreted as low level. The highest mean score in this area is 2.41, which is interpreted as a low level. This is reflected in item number 4, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I have been inspired by the deputation process prevailing in the campaign against illegal drugs compared to the model adopted in RA. 10586 and RA. 4136." The lowest mean score, on the other hand, is 2.20, which is interpreted as low level. This is reflected in items number 1 and 6.

Item number one (1) states, "As a PNP personnel, I have been deputized by LTO on RA. 10586." Item number six (6) states, "As a PNP personnel, I have investigated the death and physical injuries due to drunk and drugged driving citing RA. 10586 as deputized." The findings reveal a lesser mean of 2.20, interpreted as a low level of PNP personnel whom the LTO deputized. Because of this, a direct result is also a lesser investigation of death and injuries caused by drunk and drugged driving, respectively.

These findings confirm the study by Beary (2018), which delves into the importance of comprehensive training programs for law enforcement officers to ensure an understanding of their roles and responsibilities in enforcing traffic laws, including those related to drunk and drugged driving. By examining the impact of training initiatives on compliance and awareness levels among officers, this research can offer valuable insights into strategies for improving enforcement practices and addressing the identified implications in the context of deputation agreements.

Table 6
Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement

Area	Mean	Interpretation
C. Enforcement		
<i>As a PNP personnel, I...</i>		
1. have maintained data on drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	2.41	Low Level
2. have conducted checkpoint operations on drunk and drugged driving.	2.56	Moderate Level
3. deemed it important to have a breath analyzer and speed gun during operations.	2.62	Moderate Level
4. maintained Crime Clock for drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	2.60	Moderate Level
5. maintained Hit Map for drunk and drugged driving-related accidents.	2.58	Moderate Level
6. have been subjected to drug test parties to traffic accidents in one of my tours of duty.	2.41	Low Level
7. have subjected drunk drivers to field sobriety tests in one of my tours of duty.	2.42	Low Level
8. have subjected drunk drivers to alcoholic breath in one of my tours of duty.	2.33	Low Level
9. have filed cases citing Act No 3815 and RA 4136 on drunk and drugged driving rather than RA 10586.	2.27	Low Level
10. have strictly and religiously enforced or implemented the law against drunk and drugged driving foreseen to minimize, if not control, senseless and gruesome traffic accidents.	2.59	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	2.48	Low Level

Table 6 emphasizes the PNP Personnel's compliance level on RA—10586 in Enforcement. The overall mean is 2.48, which is interpreted as low level. The highest mean score in this area is 2.62, which is interpreted as Moderate level. This is reflected in item number 3, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I deemed it important to have a breath analyzer and speed gun during operation."

The lowest mean score is 2.27, which is interpreted as low level. This is found in item number 9, which states, "As a PNP personnel, I have filed cases citing act No. 3815 and RA. 4136 on drunk and drugged driving rather than RA. 10586."

The results show that the PNP Personnel's compliance level on RA 10586, particularly in Enforcement, is at a low level. Generally, this means there needs to be more enforcement of the law against erring motorists. The results further show that breath analyzers and speed guns are available during the operation, yet more is needed. The weakest link in this area is filing cases against erring motorists. There are many erring motorists, but few cases are filed against them. Sometimes, this is due to the court's insufficiency in meeting evidentiary requirements.

These results substantiate the study by Santos (2023), which focuses on the importance of legal compliance and the proper implementation of RA 10586 in addressing drunk and drugged driving incidents. By examining the factors influencing law enforcement officers' decision-making processes in filing cases related to impaired driving, this research can offer insights into strategies for improving adherence to specific legislation and enhancing enforcement practices to combat drugged driving offenses effectively.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 when grouped according to Selected Variables

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	138.44	8564.000	0.502	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	145	132.06				
Length of Service	Shorter	141	142.33	7990.000	0.104		Not Significant
	Longer	128	126.92				

The difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education reveals no significant differences when grouped and compared according to age and length of service with computer p-values of 0.502 and 0.104, which are greater than the significance level 0.05. Therefore, when grouped and compared according to variables, the null hypothesis that no significant difference exists in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education is accepted.

The findings suggest that for PNP personnel in the education sector, demographic factors such as age and length of service could be higher on the level of awareness regarding RA 10586. This indicates that regardless of age or length of service, PNP personnel in the education sector exhibit consistent awareness of RA 10586. Recognizing the non-significant influence of these demographic variables on awareness levels can help develop targeted training and awareness programs that cater to the needs of all personnel, irrespective of their age or length of service.

These results support the research conducted by Lockie et al. (2020), which underscores the critical role of customized training initiatives in the law enforcement sector. By focusing on developing and implementing targeted training programs, organizations can address the specific needs and knowledge gaps of personnel, leading to heightened awareness and adherence to pertinent regulations and policies. This approach enhances the effectiveness of training efforts and promotes a culture of continuous learning and compliance within law enforcement agencies.

Table 8
Difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	143.43	7944.500	0.099	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	145	127.79				
Length of Service	Shorter	141	144.04	7749.500	0.045		Significant
	Longer	128	125.04				

Results presented in Table 8 on the difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation, when grouped and compared according to age, show no significant difference as the computed p-value of 0.099 is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, when grouped and compared according to age, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in the area deputation is accepted. However, when the respondents were grouped and compared according to the length of service, the computed p-value of 0.045 is less than the level of significance of 0.05, indicating the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in the area deputation when grouped and compared according to length of service is rejected.

It implies that age does not significantly impact the level of awareness. However, for the length of service, it shows that those with a shorter length of service have higher levels of awareness in Deputation, with a mean rank of 144.04 as compared to 125.04 for a longer length of service. It means that police personnel with shorter lengths of service may have retained information from recent training sessions more effectively compared to their longer-serving counterparts. Also, they may be more receptive to new information and regulatory updates, demonstrating a greater ability to adapt to changes in laws or enforcement practices.

These findings affirm the research by Johnson (2019) underscores the critical importance of integrating tailored training programs in the law enforcement sector to address personnel's specific needs and knowledge gaps. Organizations can effectively enhance awareness and adherence to relevant regulations and policies by focusing on developing and implementing customized training initiatives. This approach improves the efficacy of training efforts and fosters continuous learning and compliance within law enforcement agencies. Moreover, by designing training programs that cater to the diverse demographic profiles of personnel, organizations can ensure that all individuals receive the necessary knowledge and skills to fulfill their responsibilities effectively.

Table 9
Difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	146.12	7611.500	0.030	0.05	Significant
	Older	145	125.49				

Length of Service	Shorter	141	145.68	7518.500	0.018	Significant
	Longer	128	123.24			

Findings shown in Table 9 on the difference in the Level of Awareness of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement reveal that there is a significant difference when grouped and compared according to age and length of service as the computed p-value of 0.030 and 0.018 is less than the significance level. Thus, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Level of Awareness of PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in the area enforcement when grouped and compared according to age and length of service is rejected.

Organizations may need to consider age and length of service factors when designing training and awareness of programs to ensure that all personnel are well-informed and compliant with relevant regulations in the enforcement sector.

These results confirm the study by Johnson (2019), which delves into the relationship between age, length of service, and awareness levels among law enforcement personnel. By highlighting the importance of tailoring training programs based on demographic factors, the research underscores the potential for enhancing awareness levels and ensuring compliance with regulations within law enforcement agencies.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 when grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Table 10
Difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	134.08	8876.500	0.858	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	145	135.78				
Length of Service	Shorter	141	142.16	8014.000	0.111		Not Significant
	Longer	128	127.11				

Results presented the difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education when grouped and compared according to age and length of service showed no significant differences as the computed p-values of 0.858 and 0.111 are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Thus, when grouped and compared according to variables, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Education is accepted.

The findings suggest that age has little impact on awareness levels. In contrast, length of service emerges as a significant factor influencing the awareness levels of PNP personnel regarding RA 10586 in the contingent area. Tailoring training and awareness initiatives based on length of service can ensure that all personnel are adequately informed and compliant with relevant regulations.

These findings conform to the study of O'Neill's (2016) research, which explores how demographic factors influence compliance behavior in law enforcement agencies. It stresses the importance of customizing training programs and awareness initiatives according to specific demographic variables like age and length of service to boost compliance levels and ensure adherence to regulatory standards. Age may have minimal impact on compliance behavior, whereas length of service significantly influences awareness levels and adherence to regulations among law enforcement personnel. By tailoring training programs based on these demographic factors, organizations can foster a compliance culture and enhance awareness levels in law enforcement agencies.

Table 11
Difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	138.42	8566.000	0.499	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	145	132.08				
Length of Service	Shorter	141	142.92	7907.000	0.075		Not Significant
	Longer	128	126.27				

As shown in the findings, the difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation when grouped and compared according to age and length of service showed no significant differences

as the computed p-value of 0.499 and 0.075 are greater than the level of significance 0.05. Therefore, when grouped and compared according to variables, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Deputation is accepted.

This implies that organizations may not need to tailor training or compliance programs specifically based on age or length of service for PNP personnel in the Deputation area. Other factors or approaches may be more relevant in promoting and ensuring compliance with RA 10586 among personnel in this sector.

These findings affirm Anthony's investigation (2018), which found that demographic factors like age and length of service may only sometimes be the primary determinants of compliance levels among PNP personnel in the deputation area. It emphasizes that organizational culture, leadership effectiveness, and the clarity of policies and procedures play a more significant role in influencing compliance within law enforcement agencies.

Table 12
Difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement when Grouped according to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	124	143.17	7977.500	0.108	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	145	128.02				
Length of Service	Shorter	141	149.05	7042.500	0.002		Significant
	Longer	128	119.52				

Data on the difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 in Enforcement, when grouped and compared according to age, showed no significant difference as the computed p-value of 0.108 is greater than the significant level of 0.05. Hence, the hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 when grouped and compared according to age is accepted. However, when the respondents were grouped and compared according to length of service, the computed p-value of 0.002 is less than the level of significance of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the Level of Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 when grouped and compared to length of service is rejected.

The findings suggest that age does not significantly impact compliance levels among PNP personnel in Enforcement. However, compliance is similar based on the length of service. Newer recruits may be more attuned to organizational expectations or more closely aligned with current training standards. At the same time, longer-serving personnel may need help keeping pace with evolving requirements or priorities. Tailoring training and compliance programs according to service size may be crucial in ensuring adherence to RA 10586 among personnel in the enforcement sector.

These findings support the study of Johnson et al. (2016), which found that customizing training programs to align with personnel's experience and service length can lead to improved compliance outcomes. Their study emphasized the importance of considering individual characteristics, such as length of service, when designing training initiatives to enhance compliance levels within law enforcement organizations.

Relational Analysis Between the Level of Awareness and Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586

Table 13
Relationship Between the Levels of Awareness and Compliance of PNP Personnel on RA 10586

Variable	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Awareness				
	1.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
Level of Compliance				

Analysis between the Level of Awareness and Compliance of the PNP Personnel on RA 10586 reveals a significant relationship, with a computed value of 0.000, less than the significance level of 0.05. Thus, the null

hypothesis that no significant relationship exists between the Level of Awareness and Level of Compliance is rejected.

This implies that awareness often stems from education and training programs. PNP personnel who are well-informed about rules, regulations, and protocols are more likely to understand the importance of compliance and adhere to them consistently. Also, increased awareness can lead to a greater sense of accountability among PNP personnel. When individuals understand the rationale behind policies and procedures, they are more likely to take responsibility for their actions and comply with organizational standards.

Additionally, increasing awareness levels among PNP personnel is a need to enhance compliance with RA 10586. Strengthening awareness initiatives may be vital in fostering a culture of compliance within the PNP and ensuring consistent adherence to relevant regulations. Expanding on the importance of awareness initiatives, organizations must implement comprehensive training programs that educate PNP personnel on the specifics of RA 10586 and emphasize the rationale behind the regulations. By providing context and highlighting the significance of compliance, personnel are more likely to internalize the importance of adhering to the rules.

These findings validate the research by Northup (2019), which focused on the effectiveness of awareness campaigns in enhancing compliance with specific regulations within law enforcement agencies. They underscored the importance of providing context and rationale behind policies and procedures to increase personnel's understanding and commitment to compliance. By implementing robust training programs emphasizing the significance of adherence to regulations like RA 10586, organizations can effectively promote a culture of compliance and accountability among PNP personnel.

Conclusion

The results indicate that the awareness of PNP personnel regarding RA 10586 was moderate, while their compliance was low. Moderate awareness means PNP personnel are somewhat aware of it, but low compliance means that even while they know the law, they are somewhat adamant about enforcing it religiously. Indeed, their level of awareness directly corresponds to or influence the extent of their compliance in education, deputation, and enforcement. The anemic compliance with the law against drunk and drugged driving over and above the general requirement of public order and safety can be attributed to the lack of awareness and wanting of a governmental system for law enforcers. A whole-of-nation or government approach should be institutionalized for the mobilization of government agencies, including local government units, with a clear oversight function from the lead agency complemented with resources to effectively discharge the mandate of the law. Engagement with local communities and stakeholders is also a welcome enhancement to promote responsible driving towards overall road safety.

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